

Phase space sampling of a non-separable hamiltonian in the Metropolis Monte-Carlo and Molecular Dynamics contexts

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Abstract

Molecular Dynamics procedures require an adequate time integrator in order to preserve the volume in the phase space (*i.e.* symplectic integrator). Non-separable hamiltonians appear as a challenge to these procedures. We investigate whether the Midpoint Euler integrator yield symplectic trajectories when applied to a non-separable hamiltonian. We focus on the Pauli potential to mimic the “Pauli exclusion principl” in small to intermediate nuclei. We compared our results to those obtained by Metropolis Monte-Carlo (MMC) samplings. The examined statistics show no significant differences between both methods. These are quite promising results for more complex simulations attaining periodic boundary conditions.

Key Words: Pauli Exclusion, Metropolis Monte-Carlo (MMC), Creutz Monte-Carlo (CMC)

1. Introduction

The “Pauli exclusion principle” expresses the fact that any two particles cannot occupy similar positions and momenta simultaneously. In the context of classical mechanics, this can be achieved by means of a repulsive potentials on either the positions and the moments of the particles. This kind of potential was introduced in Ref. [1], and it was shown that an adequate moment distribution for Fermi gases could be obtained after it. It was also observed that the Pauli potential together with Lennard-Jones and the Coulomb-type interactions allow to adequately reproduce the energies and compressibilities of nuclear matter (NM) in the saturated regime [2, 3].

Pauli potential was successfully introduced in the study of neutron-rich NM at very high densities (ten times the saturation density) [4]. Other variants of this potential were also introduced in the same context [5]. However, it was observed that in some cases the Pauli potentials can generate artificial biases in some properties Fermi gas basics [6]. Corrective expressions to the Pauli potential were proposed for these cases, although not a general solution is available yet [6].

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The Molecular Dynamics (MD) procedures present a challenge in the case of non-separable Hamiltonians. The difficulties arise in how to generate trajectories that respect the symplectic nature of the system, while allowing a computationally feasible method. The usual symplectic integrators (*i.e.* Verlet algorithm) are only explicit for Hamiltonians separable [7, 8]. If the Hamiltonian is non-separable, many of them become implicit and appear as non-feasible ones.

It is known that those integrators arising from a variational scheme yield symplectic ones. There are several discretization procedures for the implementation of these integrators. Some of them can be found in [9-12]. The Euler “midpoint” integrator belongs to this kind, although it presents (marginal) stability problems in the long term. This issue is analyzed in detail in Ref. [11] and the drawback could be solved through periodic adjustments in the medium term evolution.

The proceeding is organized as follows. In Section 2 we present the potentials and the dynamic equations. Special emphasis will be placed on Pauli’s potential. We then show the most relevant results obtained for the MD procedures in Section 3. To the extent possible, each result will be compared with its corresponding one, obtained according to MMC or CMC procedures. A short discussion on the results can be found in Section 4. The conclusions are finally outlined in Section 5.

2. Background

2.1 The model

The following is the mathematical expression for the nuclear Hamiltonian, including four species: protons *up* and *down*, and neutrons *up* and *down*):

$$\mathcal{H} = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{p_i^2}{2m} + \sum_{i<j}^N [V_N(q_{ij}) + V_C(q_{ij}) + V_P(q_{ij}, p_{ij})] \quad (1)$$

where $q_{ij} = |\mathbf{q}_i - \mathbf{q}_j|$ correspond to the distance between nucleon i and j , while $p_{ij} = |\mathbf{p}_i - \mathbf{p}_j|$ correspond to the distance between the momenta of these nucleons. The sum applies to any pair of nucleons. The expression (1) means that the hamiltonian is non-separable into terms depending on the positions q_{ij} , on one side, and terms depending on the momenta p_{ij} on the other.

The potentials in Eq. (1) represent the nuclear potential V_N , the Coulomb repulsion between charged nucleons (protons) V_C and the “Pauli exclusion principle” V_P .

The nuclear potential is considered repulsive between protons, and also between neutrons. This prevents the formation of di-neutrons, etc. On the

other hand, the interaction between neutrons and protons is of the kind of a Lennard-Jones type (modified according to [3]). The expressions are the following:

$$V_N(q_{ij}) = \begin{cases} V_{np} \left[\left(\frac{\sigma}{q_{ij}} \right)^n - \left(\frac{\sigma}{q_{ij}} \right)^m \right] & \text{neutron - proton} \\ V_{pp} \left(\frac{\sigma}{q_{ij}} \right)^n & \text{proton - proton} \\ V_{nn} \left(\frac{\sigma}{q_{ij}} \right)^n & \text{neutron - neutron} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where V_{np} , $V_{nn} = V_{pp}$, σ and n , m are estimated parameters obtained from the experimental energy levels of nuclei [3].

The Coulomb potential actuating between protons is the usual one $V_C = e^2/q_{ij}$. No screening effects due to the electronic cloud are considered here, since we only deal with nuclei alone.

The Pauli potential emulates the ‘‘Pauli exclusion principle’’ and actuates between nucleons of the same type and spin. The expression is the following:

$$V_P(q_{ij}, p_{ij}) = V_0 \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{q_{ij}^2}{q_0^2} + \frac{p_{ij}^2}{p_0^2} \right) \right] \quad (3)$$

where $q_0 = 6.0$ fm y $p_0 = 61.969$ MeV/ c are the appropriate scale factors for a Fermi gas. Las Refs.[1-3] detail the estimation procedure for both magnitudes and for V_0 .

2.2 Markov Chains

The Markov chains are implemented through the transition probabilities of the kind of Metropolis-Monte Carlo (MMC) or Creutz-Monte Carlo (CMC). The former is suitable for the canonical ensemble context and the latter for the microcanonical ensemble. The transition probabilities in the MMC case are the following [13]:

$$P_{i,i+1} = \begin{cases} e^{-\Delta\mathcal{H}/kT} & \text{si } \Delta\mathcal{H} > 0 \\ 1 & \text{si } \Delta\mathcal{H} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$\Delta\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_i - \mathcal{H}_{i-1}$ correspond to the energy jump occurring whenever a particle is moved or its momentum changed. T represents the temperature of the thermal bath.

Similarly, the transition probabilities for the CMC case are as follows:

$$P_{i,i+1} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{si } \Delta\mathcal{H} < 0 \\ 0 & \text{si } \Delta\mathcal{H} > \mathcal{H}_D \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta\mathcal{H}$ is the same as in MMC, while \mathcal{H}_D corresponds to the energy associated to the “Creutz daemon” [14]. The Creutz daemon is a somewhat energy reservoir capable of exchanging energy to the nucleons. It has an initial null value, say $\mathcal{H}_D = 0$, but after accepting any new configuration it updates to $\mathcal{H}_D = \mathcal{H}_D - \Delta\mathcal{H}$. \mathcal{H}_D is restricted, however, to positive values (including the null value).

2.3 The variational integrators

The variational integrators are those that express the least action principle from classical mechanics. This principle, in the form of the Hamilton’s equations, reads as follows:

$$\int_{\tau} \left(\dot{q}_i - \frac{\partial\mathcal{H}}{\partial p_i} \right) \delta p_i dt = 0 \quad , \quad \int_{\tau} \left(\dot{p}_i + \frac{\partial\mathcal{H}}{\partial q_i} \right) \delta q_i dt = 0 \quad (6)$$

Both equations allow a straightforward discretization of positions and momenta. The final expressions are the following:

$$\begin{cases} q_i^{n+1} = q_i^{n-1} + 2h \left(\frac{\partial\mathcal{H}}{\partial p_i} \right)_n \\ p_i^{n+1} = p_i^{n-1} - 2h \left(\frac{\partial\mathcal{H}}{\partial q_i} \right)_n \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where the truncation order is $\mathcal{O}(h^2)$. The indices stand for the values of (q_i, p_i) at the regular intervals $t = 0, h, 2h, 3h, \dots, nh, \dots$

The expressions (7) correspond to a “midpoint” Euler scheme. This scheme presents asymptotic instability in the long term, as already mentioned in Section 1. For this reason, it is suggested in the literature to restart the integrator at a medium term long through an Euler “forward” integrator [11, 15].

3. Results

In this Section we first show that the nuclear model exhibited in Section 2.1 is accurate for reproducing the empirical data of a wide range of nuclei (Section 3.1). We then move to those results associated to the cooling process when applying the MD and CMC procedures (Section 3.2). Finally, the structure and momenta of “cooled” nuclei are studied (see Sections 3.3).

3.1 Accuracy of the model

Fig. 1 shows our simulations (MD) of the energy per nucleon for a wide range of nuclei (blue circles). These are compared with experimental data appearing in the literature (red circles) [16, 17]. Notice that both match reasonably well, especially for the case of heavy nuclei. The dashed blue curve is included for a better view and corresponds to the fitting of our simulations into the Weizsäcker “liquid drop model”.

Figure 1: Energy (per nucleon) as a function of the mass number A . The experimental values and the corresponding simulated (MD-Euler) values are shown. The temperature is $T \approx 0.01$ MeV.

We further compared the MD simulations with those obtained through the Creutz (CMC) procedure. Fig. 2 details the resulting energies after a “slow” cooling process (see Section 3.2). The energies of the Metropolis Monte-Carlo (MMC) procedure are included as a reference, although they correspond to the canonical context.

The Euler and Creutz procedures exhibit quite similar results. However, the Creutz energies are always equal or slightly greater (in modulus) with respect to Euler’s. The difference is of the order of 0.25 MeV. We traced back this small discrepancy and arrived to the conclusion that it does not correspond to an artifact, but to the way in which the Creutz algorithm explores the configurational space. We will no longer continue with this line of investigation in this work.

The main conclusion that follows from the above observations is that the MD simulations replicates the experimental data reasonably well, and is an

Figure 2: Energy (per nucleon) according to the MMC (Metropolis), CMC (Creutz) and MD (Euler) procedures. The temperature is $T \approx 0.01$ MeV. The corresponding fittings are shown in dashed lines.

improvement over previously used models (see Ref.[18]). The performance of the results is similar for MD and CMC (beyond small discrepancies).

3.2 The cooling process

We next examined the energies and temperatures along the cooling process. Fig. 3 shows a few examples of the resulting nucleon structures after the cooling.

The cooling process in MD was carried out by means of the momentum re-scaling $\mathbf{p} \rightarrow \alpha \mathbf{p}$, where α is a fixed value close to unity (say, $\alpha = 0.998$), in order to accomplish a slow cooling.

The CMC cooling process was carried out by re-scaling the energy of the “Creutz daemon” $E_d \rightarrow \alpha E_d$. This energy is embedded throughout the whole nucleus, regardless of the mass number A . We verified previously that $\alpha = 0.95$ is an appropriate value for accomplishing a slow cooling rate.

Fig. 4 shows two examples of energy curves as a function of the temperature of the system for CMC and MD. Both procedures started from the same initial condition and were first cooled by means of MMC (not shown). Once the system was able to hold the structure, we applied a smooth heating and a cooling by means of CMC or MD, depending on the case (shown in the Fig. 4).

We observed a small bias of the order of 0.25 MeV between the MD and the CMC procedures (in all explored the nuclei; see Fig. 4). We further examined

Figure 3: Nuclei structures at $T_{\text{eff}} \approx 0.01$ MeV for the MD Euler procedure. The blue and violet nucleons correspond to neutrons (*up* y *down*, respectively). The orange y green nucleons correspond to protons (*up* y *down*, respectively). The red lines represent *links* for distances shorter than 2.5 fm.

this phenomenon by tracking the changes in the nucleons' positions at each step of the cooling process. We inspected many realizations of the process. We arrived to the conclusion that a single MD initial condition was not enough to explore the whole configurational space. Many realizations for different initial conditions should be carried out. But, in the end, either the MD and CMC yield similar results. We will not insist on this point in this work.

The caloric curve for the explored isotopes is shown in Fig. 5 (for the MD procedure). Notice that the heat capacity takes values $C_v > 3$, except for the Lithium isotope. The energies at $T_{\text{eff}} = 0$ can be obtained from extrapolation of the the linear fitting of the simulated data (see dashed lines in Fig. 5).

The main conclusion that follows from the analysis of the cooling process is that the CMC and MD processes do not lead to the same configurations. Different configurations can produce energy biases of the order of 0.25 MeV at the cold stage. Thus, a set of initial conditions should be explored in MD to arrive to the minimum energy configuration.

3.3 The structure

We now turn to the structure of the nuclei. Fig. 6 shows a cold Mercury nucleus. The neutrons and protons are represented in different colors (see Fig. 6(b)). Notice that two simple cubic (SC) structures appear, although somehow interlocked.

Fig. 7 details the distribution of nucleon densities as a function of the distance between them (see caption for further details). The inset shows that the first maximum for pairs of different nucleon type occurs at 2.04 fm, while the first maximum for pairs of equal type occurs at 2.37 fm. The latter is $2/\sqrt{3}$ times the former.

Figure 4: Energy (per nucleon) as a function of the temperature for Fe and Hg. A first cooling was carried out by means of the MMC procedure (not shown). Then followed a MD (Euler) or CMC (Creutz) cooling. The lines correspond to moving averages. The temperature was T_{eff} for MD and T_{creutz} for CMC.

Figure 5: Energy (per nucleon) as a function of the effective temperature (*i.e.* the MD temperature) for the explored isotopes. Data corresponds to the MD (Euler) procedure. The dashed lines correspond to the ordinary least square fitting. The inset shows the heat capacity C_v computed from the slope of the fitting lines.

Figure 6: Mercury ($A = 197, Z = 80$) at temperature $T_{\text{eff}} \approx 0.01$ MeV (MD Euler procedure). (a) The blue and violet nucleons correspond to neutrons (*up* y *down*, respectively), while the orange and green nucleons correspond to protons (*up* y *down*, respectively). (b) Neutrons represented in blue and protons in orange.

Figure 7: Radial density distribution $\rho(r) = p(r)/4\pi r^2 dr$. The horizontal axis corresponds to the reduced scale r/r_{max} , where $r_{\text{max}} = 2.04$ fm and $r_{\text{max}} = 2.37$ fm for the links connecting nucleons of different type or the same type, respectively. The inset shows the density $\rho(r)$ as a function of the real scale. The MD procedure was used and the shown temperature is $T \approx 0.01$ MeV. Averages were taken over 200 realizations.

The plot in Fig. 7 presents the horizontal axis on a normalized scale with respect to the first neighbors (see caption). A quick inspection shows that the maxima coincide with the relative distances expected for an SC arrangement. The maxima for equal species appear at 1, $\sqrt{2}$ and $\sqrt{3}$. These three maxima occur at distances smaller than the Pauli distance $q_0 = 6$ fm (see Section 2.1), which indicates that the Pauli exclusion should be present. However, the intensity of the Pauli repulsion will depend on the momenta of neighboring nucleons.

The above observations may be summarized as follows: the Pauli potential is somehow responsible for the existence of two “interlocked” or “entangled” structures, one for neutrons and one for protons. Both are similar and take the form of an SC arrangement. This was not observed previously in completely classical nuclear systems (to our knowledge).

4. Discussion

This Section discusses the main topics outlined in Section 3. We divide the discussion into two parts: one related to the cooling process, and the other to the structure of the isotope, at the cold stage.

Discussion on the cooling process

We noticed in Section 3.2 that the CMC cooling procedure yields configurations of minimum energy (with respect to MD). The reason for this is that the MD procedure does not explore adequately the configurational space, since the possible MD trajectories are restricted by the initial conditions. Thus, many realizations should be carried out (with varying initial conditions) in order to arrive to a true minimum energy configuration.

The CMC procedure appears as a better choice with respect to MD when cooling down isotopes. However, other matters should be taken into account.

- (a) The “Creutz daemon” exchanges energy with all the particles in the system. As the mass number A increases (*i.e.* heavy nuclei), each nucleon can exchange smaller amounts of energy because the daemon energy has to be shared with many other nucleons. Thus, any new accepted configuration will be highly correlated with the old one. The whole process slows down and it takes many steps to reach a quite dissimilar configuration.
- (b) The energy E_d of the “Creutz daemon” is associated to the microcanonical temperature through its mean value $T = \langle E_d \rangle$. This means that E_d accomplished smaller values as the system cools down. Consequently, the energy exchange with the nucleons becomes harder and the

successive configurations appear as more correlated. The whole process slows down.

The above arguments express that cold nuclei or heavy ones are not completely feasible under the CMC context. This is a relevant matter when choosing to proceed with CMC or MD.

Discussion on the structure of cold nuclei

We analyzed the spatial structure of cold nuclei in Section 3.3. We showed that the Pauli potential is responsible for the existence of two “entangled” or “interlocked” SC arrangements.

The “entangled” SC structures ensure that any proton (or neutron) will occupy the center of a cubic cell of neutrons (or protons). Thus, any proton (or neutron) will be surrounded by 8 neutrons (or protons) (see Fig. 6). This actually means that the nuclear energy attains a minimum in the cell, and this minimum is roughly $E_{\min} \approx 8 \times (-5 \text{ MeV})$, according to the proton- neutron expression in (2). The nuclear minimum balances the repulsion due to any other neighbor of the same specie. Notice, however, that the net energy must be negative to keep the structure stable.

Fig. 8 summarizes the above. It can be seen there the mean neutron-proton (NP) energy and the Pauli energy for concentric shells with respect to the center of mass (see caption for details). The NN and PP energies (including Coulomb) are not plotted in Fig. 8 since these are not relevant for this analysis.

The inner nucleons in Fig. 8 (say, $r < 7 \text{ fm}$) exhibit an overall negative energy. But the energy of the NP bond diminish as the nucleus radius increases. This energy becomes completely balanced with the Pauli energy in the outer most shell of the nucleus (see Fig. 8). This leaves very little room for any other energy and for kinetic energy.

The decrease in the NP energy intensity in the outer most shells of the nucleus can be explained by the decrease in the number of neighbors in the outer shells. Fig. 9 confirms this by accounting the amount of first NP neighbors. The values shown in Fig. 9 were rounded to the nearest integer (see caption for details).

We conclude that there is a correspondence between the decrease of neighboring nucleons and the decrease of the mean NP energy, as the radius increases. But it should be noted that the decrease in the number of neighbors can not be related easily to the Pauli repulsion energy, since this depends also on the difference between neighboring momenta (of the same species).

Figure 8: Mean energy (per nucleon) as a function of the distance from the center of mass. The bins correspond to spherical shells at increasing radii. The blue bins correspond to the mean nuclear energy between proton and neutron. The orange bins correspond to the Pauli energy. Data was acquired from MD (Euler) simulations en at $T \approx 0.01$ MeV. Mean values run over 30 configurations. The red lines represent the errors at $\pm\sigma$.

Figure 9: Number of nucleons involved in NP bonds per unit cell as a function of concentric shells. The horizontal axis corresponds to the distance of the shell with respect to the center of mass. Data in the vertical axis was rounded to the nearest integer. Two clasifying criteria were followed for accounting the links: those links attaining a distance less than $r_c = 2.1$ fm are represented in violet, while those less than $r_c = 2.5$ fm are represented in red. $N_{\text{cell}} = 2$ corresponds to the maximum number of neighbors in the cell (say $1 + 8 \times (1/8) = 2$). The simulation was carried out by means of MD (Euler integrator) and the temperature was $T \approx 0.01$ MeV. A total of 30 configurations were considered.

5. Conclusions

The investigation explores the presence of a non-separable potential that mimics the “Pauli exclusion principle” in the context of a classic hamiltonian system. This potential was proposed by Dr. Claudio Dorso when studying either finite and infinite nuclear systems. Here we limit ourselves to the study of finite nuclei.

We introduced stochastic (*i.e* Metropolis Monte-Carlo and Creutz) and molecular dynamics (Euler) methods. The latter are of great interest due to its applicability in the study of collisions nuclear. All methods converged to the same results, within a small discrepancy (of the order of 0.25 MeV for the energy estimates).

Our computed energy levels were compared with experimental data published throughout the literature. The model used here replicated reasonably well these data, while it accomplished an improvement over previous models (see Ref. [1]).

We further studied the consequences of introducing the “Pauli exclusion” on finite nuclei. Two conclusions were reached:

- The Pauli potential introduces “entangled” structures of protons and neutrons (within the explored nuclei). Both are similar and take the form of a *simple cubic* (SC) arrangement. The whole system resembles a *body centered cubic* (BCC) arrangement.
- The magnitude of the momenta changes with the distance to the center of mass of the atomic nucleus (for the explored nuclei). The outer nucleons present a lower momentum (in module) than the inner ones. This does not occur in classical nuclear systems with no Pauli potential.

We finally focused on the outer most shells of the atomic nuclei. We concluded the following:

- (a) The decrease in the number of neighbors leads to a decrease in in the number of NP and Pauli (same species) links.
- (b) The linked nucleons exhibit low kinteic energy, that is, low momenta (modulus). This corresponds to intense Pauli replusions between similar species.
- (c) The total Pauli repulsion is the add-up of intense repulsions, although between a small amount of neighbors.

Our general conclusion is that the nucleons attaining intense momenta (modulus) occupy the inner part of the nucleus, where many NP bonds

exist and, consequently, higher kinetic energies may be allowed. On the contrary, the outer part of the nucleus should reduce the momenta in order to achieve a balance between the nuclear binding energies and the Pauli repulsion. In other words, the crust only admits low kinetic energies (say, low momenta in modulus) to remain stable.

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